

Clinical, radiological, and serological assessment of the efficacy and safety of nintedanib compared to pirfenidone in a sample of Iraqi patients with idiopathic pulmonary fibrosis: A retrospective cohort study

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Abstract

This study compares the treatment effects after six months of therapy with nintedanib and pirfenidone in patients with idiopathic pulmonary fibrosis (IPF) by comprehensively analyzing key parameters and establishing the diagnostic performance of two biomarkers, Krebs von den Lungen-6 (KL-6) and CC chemokine Ligand-18 (CCL-18), to predict treatment outcomes. In a hospital-based retrospective cohort study, 75 patients diagnosed with IPF were divided into three groups based on their treatment: the newly diagnosed group, which included newly diagnosed IPF patients without receiving any antifibrotic treatment (25 patients), IPF patients on pirfenidone treatment (26 patients), and IPF patients on nintedanib treatment (24 patients). After adjustment for age, sex, body mass index, and baseline values of predicted forced vital capacity (FVC_p), there was no significant difference in the rate of changes after 24 weeks of follow-up for FVC_p (-0.2 ± 0.6 , 0.0 ± 2.3 , and 0.8 ± 3.5 ml change after 4, 12, and 24 weeks for pirfenidone) and (-1.7 ± 5.9 , 1.0 ± 8.9 , and 1.4 ± 9.5 ml change after 4, 12, and 24 weeks for nintedanib). CCL-18 offers a better ability to predict radiological findings than KL-6. Most side effects were minor and included diarrhea, stomach pain, skin rash, and hyperpigmentation. In conclusion, both drugs have demonstrated the capacity to postpone the beginning stages of FVC_p decrease and lung function decline. There was little difference between the efficacy of nintedanib and pirfenidone. Both drugs were safe and well tolerated for the treatment of IPF.

Keywords

idiopathic pulmonary fibrosis, nintedanib, pirfenidone, Krebs von den Lungen-6, CC chemokine ligand 18

Introduction

Idiopathic pulmonary fibrosis (IPF), often referred to as cryptogenic fibrosing Alveolitis, is a specific kind of

fibrosing interstitial pneumonia that exclusively targets the lungs in adults and is characterized by its persistent and progressive nature (Hussein et al. 2017; Spagnolo et al. 2021).

Idiopathic pulmonary fibrosis (IPF) is a progressive, fatal fibrotic lung disease predominantly affecting middle-aged and older individuals. It is a significant contributor to morbidity and mortality. As life expectancy increases, the economic burden of IPF is anticipated to climb consistently in the foreseeable future. The precise pathophysiological mechanisms behind IPF remain unidentified. The prevailing paradigm posits that idiopathic pulmonary fibrosis (IPF) arises from persistent or recurrent damage to the lung epithelium, leading to the activation of fibroblasts and the development of myofibroblasts. The enduring myofibroblast phenotype results in excessive extracellular matrix (ECM) deposition and abnormal lung repair, causing tissue scarring, distortion of alveolar architecture, and irreversible lung function loss (Mei et al. 2022; Shakeel et al. 2023; Hussein et al. 2024a; Hussein et al. 2024b). The connection is established between the histopathologic and/or radiologic patterns of usual interstitial pneumonia (UIP), as demonstrated by high-resolution computed tomography (HRCT) and lung histology (Mustafa et al. 2015; Phan et al. 2021). A decreased lung function, lung tissue, and structure damage, reduced lung flexibility, and impaired gas exchange characterize IPF (Meltzer and Noble 2008). Symptoms include difficulty breathing during physical activity and coughing (Meltzer and Noble 2008). Within a period of three to five years after being diagnosed, this incapacitating illness always results in respiratory failure and, ultimately, death (Glass et al. 2020; Dawood et al. 2021).

The primary treatment for IPF until 2014 involved using a combination of prednisone, azathioprine, and N-acetylcysteine (Glass et al. 2022). While steroids are still utilized for cough reduction, immunosuppressants such as cyclophosphamide and mycophenolate are no longer advised for individuals with IPF due to their lack of efficacy in clinical trials (Vigeland et al. 2017). Pirfenidone and nintedanib are the two antifibrotic medications approved for treating IPF (Cerri et al. 2019). Pirfenidone is a pyridine derivative with antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and antifibrotic properties (Antar et al. 2022). It is associated with a reduction in collagen production, a reduction in the pace at which forced vital capacity (FVC) is reduced, and the progression of fibrosis is slowed by reducing the levels of the cytokine transforming growth factor- β (TGF- β) (Abd Ali et al. 2018; Mohammed et al. 2021; Antar et al. 2022). While pirfenidone is generally well-tolerated, common adverse effects include skin rash, weight loss, nausea, and exhaustion (Lancaster et al. 2017). Additionally, liver abnormalities have been reported. Consequently, individuals on pirfenidone must regularly monitor their liver function (Dhooria et al. 2020).

Nintedanib, an intracellular tyrosine kinase inhibitor (TKI), blocks the signaling pathways linked to vascular endothelial growth factor (VEGF) receptor, fibroblast growth factor (FGF) receptor 1–3, and platelet-derived growth factor receptor α and β (Petnak et al. 2021; Falih and Rakad 2023). It achieves this by attaching itself to certain places on adenosine triphosphate molecules. The effects on the receptor of tyrosine kinases lead to decreased fibroblast activity (Wind et al. 2019).

Krebs von den Lungen-6 (KL-6) is a glycoprotein with a large molecular weight found on the outer surface of bronchial epithelial cells and alveolar type II cells (Lederer et al. 2023). This chemokine can stimulate pulmonary fibroblasts' movement, growth, and survival. The potential of KL-6 as a biomarker is being increasingly investigated (Huang et al. 2021). Reports indicate that KL-6 levels are significantly elevated in patients with interstitial lung disease (ILD) compared to both healthy individuals and those with non-ILD lung diseases (Zhu et al. 2024).

The CC-chemokine ligand 18 (CCL18) is constitutively expressed by antigen-presenting cells, particularly dendritic cells and macrophages in lung tissues, and is highly inducible by inflammatory stimuli (Ascar and Hameed 2021). CCL18 gene expression and protein production are upregulated in normal alveolar macrophages (AMs) after T-helper (Th)-2 cytokine stimulation. They also revealed positive feedback between AMs and fibroblasts in promoting collagen production, as culture supernatants of AMs from IPF patients led to increased collagen production by normal lung fibroblasts through CCL18 release (Drakopanagiotakis et al. 2018; Tomos et al. 2023).

The current approach in diagnosing IPF includes clinical features (Douglas et al. 2000; Raghu et al. 2006), radiological findings using HRCT features (Raghu et al. 2011), histopathological findings for uncertain IPF, which can occur in approximately a third of the cases (Raghu et al. 2011), and routine serological markers to exclude connective tissue diseases (Raghu et al. 2011).

In this study, we hypothesized that IPF patients would show a reduction in biomarker levels during the treatment course. Since both biomarkers (KL-6 and CCL18) are elevated in active pulmonary disease, a reduction in the levels of both markers will indicate a reduction in disease activity. Preliminary studies showed that KL-6 and CCL18 have the best promise in the diagnosis of IPF, among other currently available biomarkers (Ohnishi et al. 2002; Satoh et al. 2006; Prasse et al. 2007; Prasse et al. 2009).

Globally, few studies have compared nintedanib and pirfenidone. In the first-ever real-world comparative observational study, Cerri et al. investigated the effects of the two drugs in IPF patients. They discovered that over 24 months, nintedanib and pirfenidone delayed the decline in FVC compared to non-treated individuals (Cerri et al. 2019). Cameli et al., in their real-life retrospective comparison of the long-term effectiveness of the two antifibrotic drugs for IPF, showed similar efficacy in reducing functional deterioration and improving life expectancy, associated with acceptable tolerability, even in subjects with greater functional impairment (Cameli et al. 2020). Kim et al. found that in a clinical trial, patients with IPF who used nintedanib had a slower 12-month FVC decline than pirfenidone in a post hoc analysis (Kim et al. 2024). Clinical trials worldwide have shown that both medications improved the outcome of IPF, irrespective of age, sex, and ethnicity. Except for some adverse drug reactions, there was little difference between the efficacy of nintedanib and pirfenidone. Both drugs were safe and well tolerated for treating IPF (Nafie

Hameed et al. 2008; Sabbar et al. 2023; Man et al. 2024). However, medical professionals are facing huge challenges in the use of these drugs for the treatment of IPF patients because, firstly, the mechanisms of these medications are still being investigated. Secondly, their effectiveness, tolerability, and safety vary from patient to patient and depend on how quickly the treatment is initiated (Man et al. 2024).

Based on recent guidelines (Raghu et al. 2022), nintedanib and pirfenidone received conditional recommendations for IPF in patients who have failed standard management for fibrotic ILD. The guideline committee also gave recommendations to determine and validate serum biomarkers to identify those at risk of PPF and predict outcomes, which was the major drive for this study (Raghu et al. 2022).

The current study is the first hospital-based study to document the Iraqi patients' experience treating IPF with nintedanib and pirfenidone. It is also the first to document the treatment's clinical, radiological, and serological effects with nintedanib (Ofev[®]) and compare it with pirfenidone among Iraqi patients. This study aimed to compare the effects of nintedanib and pirfenidone among Iraqi patients with IPF.

Patients and methods

Study design and settings

In a hospital-based retrospective cohort study, 75 patients diagnosed with IPF were divided into three groups based on their treatment: the newly diagnosed group, which included newly diagnosed IPF patients without receiving any antifibrotic treatment (25 patients), IPF patients on pirfenidone treatment (26 patients), and IPF patients on nintedanib treatment (24 patients), as illustrated in Fig. 1. Full patient information was recorded from our hospital's records. The study was conducted at Baghdad Teaching Hospital in Baghdad, Iraq, between December 2023 and May 2024.

Ethical consideration

The study adhered to the protocols outlined by the College of Medicine Ethics Committee at Baghdad University, approval number 03–14, on 22nd April 2023. Written informed consent was obtained from the patients.

Inclusion criteria

The study included individuals 18 years and older who had been previously diagnosed with IPF.

Exclusion criteria

Exclusion criteria included age less than 18 years (children), refusal to participate, use of drugs other than nintedanib and pirfenidone for IPF, other respiratory diseases aside from IPF, current or past diagnosis with cancer, pregnancy, breastfeeding, malignancy, heart failure, active tuberculosis, patients on biological treatment, active infection, elevated liver enzymes, and patients with a high risk of bleeding (e.g., patients on anticoagulants, antifibrotics, and high doses of antiplatelets).

Participants

The patients received treatment protocols prescribed by physicians at Baghdad Teaching Hospital's respiratory center in Baghdad, Iraq. Twenty-four received nintedanib in 100 or 150 mg dosages twice daily, the originator brand (Ofev[®]), and 26 received pirfenidone in 400 or 600 mg three times daily.

To manage adverse events, dose interruption or reduction from 150 mg twice daily to 100 mg twice daily was allowed. After an adverse event is resolved, the dose could be reinstated at 150 mg twice daily.

Figure 1. Flow chart of the study.

Data collection

The collected data included demographic variables (age, sex, body mass index (BMI), smoking history), past medical history, past and current treatment, duration of respiratory symptoms, family history of ILD, date of IPF diagnosis, duration of respiratory symptoms till treatment with antifibrotic agents, dose of antifibrotic agents, and other chronic disease. All information was collected from patient records and a separate questionnaire. Records with missing data were disregarded from further analysis; all case files included in the study had complete information.

The PFT process was conducted with spirometers under the guidance of a highly skilled technician. Spirometric testing was conducted following criteria published by the American Thoracic Society and the European Respiratory Society (Miller et al. 2005; Hussain et al. 2010; Ahmad et al. 2015).

The PFT parameters were recorded over three performances as part of their regular follow-up for IPF treatment, and the best findings were documented. Each patient's predicted forced vital capacity (FVC_p in ml) (Abd Ala et al. 2023) and SPO₂% were recorded.

The Modified Medical Research Council (mMRC) scale is a self-assessment tool used to measure the impact of breathlessness on daily activities. It rates the level of disability on a scale from 0 to 4. A score of 0 indicates no breathlessness except during strenuous exercise. A score of 1 indicates shortness of breath when hurrying on level ground or walking up a slight hill. A score of 2 indicates walking slower than people of the same age due to breathlessness or needing to stop to catch one's breath when walking at their own pace on level ground. A score of 3 indicates needing to stop for breath after walking approximately 100 meters or after a few minutes on level ground. A score of 4 indicates being too breathless to leave the house or experiencing breathlessness when dressing or undressing (Mahler and Wells 1988; Bestall et al. 1999).

All parameters were measured and assessed at baseline, 4, 12, and 24 weeks of therapy.

High-resolution computed tomography (HRCT)

Baseline HRCT scans were conducted without using a contrast medium before the initiation of treatment with either nintedanib or pirfenidone. Follow-up scans were performed after six months of treatment. This study assessed the frequency of three Usual Interstitial Pneumonia (UIP) patterns: usual, probable, and indeterminate (Fadhil et al. 2018; Hariri et al. 2020).

The predictive significance of HRCT findings, namely changes in ground-glass opacities (GGO) and honeycombing, was examined in all individuals diagnosed with IPF. CT scans were conducted while the patient held their breath during a deep inhalation. A radiologist, unaware of the patients' names, evaluated the photos.

Estimation of Krebs von den Lungen-6 (KL-6) and CC chemokine Ligand-18 (CCL-18)

The KL-6 and CCL-18 (My BioSource, USA) were measured using the competitive inhibition enzyme immunoassay technique, according to the manufacturer's instructions.

Sample size

Using the G.Power program, the sample size was estimated to be 75, assuming three groups using the F-test family with alpha = 0.05, power = 0.80, and an effect size of 0.37.

Statistical analysis

The Anderson Darling test for normality was performed, and continuous variables that were normally distributed were analyzed using one-way ANOVA with a *post hoc* Tukey test. In contrast, non-normally distributed variables were analyzed using the Kruskal-Wallis and *post hoc* Dunn's multiple comparisons tests. A two-way ANOVA repeated measure analysis was used to analyze the differences between pirfenidone and nintedanib after adjusting for age, sex, BMI, and baseline values for FVC_p, mMRC, and SPO₂%. Chi-square analysis was used for categorical variables, while linear correlation was used to assess the relationship between pulmonary function variables and investigated biomarkers. The receiver operator curve (ROC) is used to assess the diagnostic validity of the biomarkers to predict HRCT changes after six months. All analyses were conducted using GraphPad Prism version 10.2.3 and MedCalc version 14.8. A p-value was considered significant if ≤ 0.05 .

Results

Demographic and disease characters

The study included 75 patients diagnosed with idiopathic pulmonary fibrosis, of whom 36 (48.0%) were males, and 39 (51.0%) were females. The mean age was 56.7 ± 9.6 years, body mass index (BMI) was 27.6 ± 4.5 kg/m², 21 (72.0%) were smokers, 3 (4.0%) had a positive family history of ILD/chronic lung disease. The median (interquartile range (IQR) duration of respiratory symptoms was 2 (2–3) years, and the median (IQR) duration from the onset of respiratory symptoms to diagnosis was 3 (2–5.25) months. Regarding comorbid diseases; 32 (42.7%) had hypertension, and 5 (6.7%) had diabetes mellitus.

Table 1 illustrates the age, sex, and BMI between the three study groups. Additionally, FVC_p and SPO₂% showed no significant difference at baseline, while mMRC was significantly higher in the nintedanib group compared to the IPF without treatment group, as seen in Fig. 2.

Figure 2. Assessment of IPF patient variables. **A.** FVC_p; **B.** SPO₂%; and **C.** mMRC.

Table 1. Assessment of demographic data according to study groups.

Variables	Without treatment group	Pirfenidone group	Nintedanib group
Age, mean ± SD (y)	58.7 ± 8.9	55.3 ± 9.2	56.1 ± 10.7
Sex, n (%)			
Female	13(52.0%)	14(53.8%)	12(50.0%)
Male	12(48.0%)	12(46.2%)	12(50.0%)
BMI, mean ± SD (kg/m ²)	26.4 ± 3.9	27.0 ± 4.1	29.4 ± 4.9

SD: standard deviation, n: number, BMI: body mass index

Change in FVC_p, SPO₂%, and mMRC

At baseline, there was no significant difference in FVC_p between pirfenidone and nintedanib (45.3 ± 5.5 vs. 51.0 ± 16.8 ml); after four weeks, no significant change was observed (45.1 ± 5.7 vs. 49.3 ± 15.9 ml); after 12 weeks, no significant difference was seen (45.3 ± 5.1 vs. 52.0 ± 15.5 ml); and after 24 weeks, no significant difference was seen (46.2 ± 4.7 vs. 52.4 ± 14.9 ml), as illustrated in Fig. 3A.

Figure 3. Comparison between pirfenidone and nintedanib absolute value and change from baseline over 24 weeks follow-up in **A.** change in FVC_p; **B.** absolute FVC_p value; **C.** change in SPO₂%; **D.** absolute SPO₂% value; **E.** change in mMRC; and **F.** absolute mMRC value.

We performed a two-way ANOVA analysis to analyze the differences between pirfenidone and nintedanib after adjustment to age, sex, BMI, and baseline FVC_p value. There was no significant difference in the rate of changes after 24 weeks of follow-up (-0.2 ± 0.6 , 0.0 ± 2.3 , and 0.8 ± 3.5 ml change after 4, 12, and 24 weeks for pirfenidone) and (-1.7 ± 5.9 , 1.0 ± 8.9 , and 1.4 ± 9.5 ml change after 4, 12, and 24 weeks for nintedanib), as seen in Fig. 3B.

At baseline, there was no significant difference in SPO₂% between pirfenidone and nintedanib (88.3 ± 5.3 vs. $89.1 \pm 4.4\%$); after four weeks, no significant change was observed (89.3 ± 6.1 vs. $90.6 \pm 4.5\%$); after 12 weeks, no significant difference was seen (93.5 ± 3.6 vs. $93.0 \pm 4.8\%$); and after 24 weeks, there was a significant difference seen (95.0 ± 3.3 vs. $93.4 \pm 4.1\%$, p -value = 0.019), as illustrated in Fig. 3C.

We performed a two-way ANOVA analysis to analyze the differences between pirfenidone and nintedanib after adjustment to age, sex, BMI, and baseline SPO₂% value. There was a significant difference in the rate of changes after 24 weeks of follow-up in favor of pirfenidone (1.0 ± 1.9 , 5.2 ± 3.8 , and $6.7 \pm 3.9\%$ change after 4, 12, and 24 weeks for pirfenidone) and (1.5 ± 2.8 , 4.0 ± 4.6 , and $4.3 \pm 4.2\%$ change after 4, 12, and 24 weeks for nintedanib), as seen in Fig. 3D.

At baseline, there was no significant difference in mMRC between pirfenidone and nintedanib (3.0 ± 0.7 vs. 3.4 ± 0.8 , p -value = 0.060); after four weeks, a significant change was observed (3.0 ± 0.7 vs. 3.4 ± 0.8 , p -value = 0.037); after 12 weeks, no significant difference was seen (2.9 ± 0.7 vs. 3.0 ± 1.0); and after 24 weeks, there was no significant difference seen (2.5 ± 0.9 vs. 2.7 ± 1.1), as illustrated in Fig. 3E.

We performed a two-way ANOVA analysis to analyze the differences between pirfenidone and nintedanib after adjustment to age, sex, BMI, and baseline mMRC value. There was a significant difference in the rate of changes after 24 weeks of follow-up in favor of pirfenidone (0.0 ± 0.0 , -0.1 ± 0.3 , and -0.5 ± 0.6 change after 4, 12, and 24 weeks for pirfenidone) and (0.0 ± 0.2 , -0.3 ± 0.6 , and -0.7 ± 0.8 change after 4, 12, and 24 weeks for nintedanib), as seen in Fig. 3F.

Radiological findings

The HRCT examination was performed at baseline for individuals in the pirfenidone and nintedanib treatment groups (Figs 4, 5). HRCT findings indicated that 69.23% of patients in the pirfenidone treatment group were classified as typical UIP, while 30.76% were probable UIP. Furthermore, the loop distribution was bilateral in the lower and upper lobes, at 100% in all cases. Regarding the adjacency to pleura, patients (92.3%) showed subpleural in the upper and lower lobes, while the rest (7.69%) were subpleural in the lower lobe only. Regarding the nintedanib treatment group, HRCT findings indicated that 41.66% of patients were classified as typical UIP, while 51.16% were probable UIP and 4.16% were indeterminate UIP. Furthermore, the loop distribution was bilateral in the lower and upper lobes, at 100% in all cases. Regarding the adjacency to pleura, patients (75%) showed subpleural in the upper and lower lobes. The rest (20.8%) were subpleural in the lower lobe, and only 4.16% demonstrated subpleural thickened bands, as seen in Fig. 6A, B).

The changes in the HRCT findings regarding GGO and consolidation, honeycombing, and reticulation for patients with IPF treated for more than 24 weeks with nintedanib were compared to those treated for pirfenidone. It can be seen that a lower percentage of patients on pirfenidone showed increased GGO lesions in comparison with the nintedanib treatment group. On the other hand, a higher percentage of patients on nintedanib showed decreased GGO lesions compared to those on pirfenidone treatment (50% versus 46.15%); however, these differences did not reach statistical significance, as illustrated in Fig. 4C.

On the other hand, honeycombing and reticulation were increased in 12.5% of IPF patients treated with nintedanib compared to 23.07% of those treated with pirfenidone. Unchanged honeycombing was reported in 87.5% of IPF patients treated with nintedanib versus 76.92% of those treated with pirfenidone; however, these differences did not reach statistical significance, as illustrated in Fig. 4D.

Figure 4. Chest HRCT for patients with IPF: A. Before treatment showing GGO, mosaicism, and non-prominent traction bronchiectasis; B. After 6 months of treatment with nintedanib showing less dense GGO and more clear traction bronchiectasis, especially in the lower lobe.

Figure 5. Chest HRCT for patients with IPF: **A.** Before treatment showing upper and lower lobes GGO and reticulation and non-prominent traction bronchiectasis; **B.** After 6 months of treatment with pirfenidone showing less GGO and more prominent honeycombing and traction bronchiectasis and bronchiectasis.

Figure 6. Radiological findings. **A.** HRCT findings at baseline; **B.** Adjutant to pleura findings; **C.** Ground glass opacities findings change after 24 weeks; **D.** Honeycombing and reticulation findings change after 24 weeks.

KL-6 and CCL-18 markers

Both KL-6 (663.0, 700.2, and 789.5 IU/ml median levels in the nintedanib group, pirfenidone group, and IPF without treatment group, respectively) and CCL-18 (3452, 3810, and 4111 pg/ml median levels in the nintedanib group, pirfenidone group, and IPF without treatment group, respectively) levels were significantly lower in pirfenidone and nintedanib treatment groups compared to IPF without treatment. In contrast, treatment with nintedanib showed a significantly lower value of KL-6 compared to those treated with pirfenidone, as seen in Fig. 7.

Fig. 8 shows a direct, strong correlation between KL-6 and CCL-18 in patients with IPF without treatment. Both biomarkers showed an inverse correlation with FVC_p and SPO₂% and a directed significant correlation with mMRC, as seen in Table 2.

In the pirfenidone group, CCL-18 showed an inverse correlation with SPO₂% absolute value after 24 weeks and a direct correlation with mMRC absolute value after 24 weeks; the rest of the variables did not correlate significantly with CCL-18. Meanwhile, KL-6 did not correlate with the pulmonary function assessment parameters, as illustrated in Table 3.

Figure 7. Truncated violin plot for IPF patient biomarkers. **A.** KL-6 levels, and **B.** CCL-18 levels.

Figure 8. Scatterplot of KL-6 and CCL-18 in IPF patients without treatment.

Table 2. Spearman correlation between investigated markers with pulmonary assessment variables without treatment.

Variables		KL-6	CCL-18
FVC _p	R	-0.592	-0.735
	p-value	0.002 [#]	<0.001 [#]
SPO ₂ %	R	-0.477	-0.631
	p-value	0.016 [#]	0.001 [#]
mMRC	R	0.637	0.923
	p-value	0.001 [#]	<0.001 [#]

Indicate significant differences, r: correlation coefficient.

For the nintedanib group, KL-6 showed an inverse correlation with an absolute FVC_p value after 24 weeks and a direct correlation with an absolute mMRC value after 24 weeks; the rest of the variables did not correlate significantly with KL-6. CCL-18 showed a direct correlation with an absolute mMRC value after 24 weeks and a direct correlation with the change in mMRC after 24 weeks of therapy, as illustrated in Table 3.

To assess if the investigated markers can predict worsening in radiological findings after six months of treatment (increase vs. same or reduction in honeycombing and reticulation or GGO), receiver operator curve (ROC) analysis was undertaken, and it showed that CCL-18 offers the better ability to predict radiological findings compared to KL-6; however, both biomarkers

Table 3. Correlation between investigated biomarkers and pulmonary assessment variables at the end of the follow-up period.

Variables		Pirfenidone group		Nintedanib group	
		KL-6	CCL-18	KL-6	CCL-18
FVC _p at 24 weeks	R	0.000	-0.293	-0.510	-0.381
	p-value	1.000	0.146	0.011 [#]	0.067
SPO ₂ % at 24 weeks	R	-0.165	-0.432	-0.373	-0.357
	p-value	0.421	0.028 [#]	0.073	0.087
mMRC at 24 weeks	R	0.241	0.527	0.636	0.579
	p-value	0.236	0.006 [#]	0.001 [#]	0.003 [#]
Change in FVC _p	R	0.166	-0.058	-0.279	-0.333
	p-value	0.416	0.777	0.186	0.111
Change in SPO ₂ %	R	0.225	0.308	0.114	-0.146
	p-value	0.270	0.126	0.597	0.495
Change in mMRC	R	-0.032	0.169	0.392	0.526
	p-value	0.877	0.409	0.058	0.008 [#]

indicate significant differences, r: correlation coefficient.

Figure 9. ROC curve analysis of biomarkers predicting HRCT change after 24 weeks of treatment. (AUC for KL-8 = 0.565, and for CCL-18 = 0.640).

resulted in area under the curve (AUC) below 0.7, indicating a poor ability to predict radiological response, as illustrated in Fig. 9.

Side effects

Several side effects were reported with Pirfenidone treatment, represented by diarrhea, stomach pain, skin rash, and hyperpigmentation, as shown in Table 4. Stomach pain, hyperpigmentation, and skin rash were significantly higher in the pirfenidone group compared to the nintedanib group, as seen in Table 4.

Table 4. Side effects profile of pirfenidone and nintedanib-treated IPF patients.

Side effects	Nintedanib	Pirfenidone	P-value
Diarrhea	11 (45.83 %)	10 (38.46%)	0.775
Stomach pain	0 (0%)	8 (30.76%)	0.004
Hyperpigmentation	0 (0%)	12 (46.15%)	0.002
Skin rash	0 (0%)	12 (46.15%)	0.002
Dyspepsia	1 (2.7%)	0 (0%)	0.480
Elevation of AST	2 (5.4%)	0 (0%)	0.490
Elevation of ALT	2 (5.4%)	0 (0%)	0.490
Elevation of ALP	1 (2.7%)	0 (0%)	0.480

Discussion

IPF is a persistent, distressing, and advancing respiratory condition that results in permanent scarring of the lung tissue and a deterioration in lung capacity (Galioto et al. 2020). The clinical course of IPF is variable, and the prognosis is highly poor, with a survival rate of roughly 2–5 years (Hadi et al. 2023). The goal of treatment is to reduce or stabilize the disease progression and to prevent acute exacerbations, which may be fatal in 5–15% of patients (Sadon et al. 2020). The traditional treatment for IPF was steroids, anti-inflammatory drugs, and immunosuppressive drugs such as azathioprine, but these drugs showed poor efficacy and failed to prevent disease progression (Sadon et al. 2020). The emergence of new antifibrotic therapies for IPF has given considerable hope to IPF patients (Pleasant and Tighe 2019).

In recent years, the treatment of IPF has been significantly improved due to the introduction of antifibrotic agents (Thong et al. 2023). In the present study, we have demonstrated the comparative effect of pirfenidone and Nintedanib on FVC_p , $SPO_2\%$, mMRC scale, and HRCT findings after 24 weeks of therapy. Both groups showed improvement in the FVC_p , $SPO_2\%$, mMRC score, and radiological findings at the end of the follow-up.

Similar results were reported by Sadon et al., who showed improved oxygen saturation during the treatment with nintedanib and pirfenidone (Sadon et al. 2020). Another study showed that the mMRC scale decreased in ILD patients due to using nintedanib (Magnani et al. 2023). With the nintedanib treatment, FVC_p improved slightly higher than the pirfenidone treatment after 24 weeks of therapy. These results were similar to those reported by Man et al., who found that both drugs demonstrated the capacity to postpone the beginning stages of FVC_p decrease and lung function decline (Man et al.

2024). Similar findings were reported by another study that documented a valuable therapeutic benefit of both drugs in reducing the rate of decline in pulmonary function (Kim et al. 2024). Flaherty et al. reported an annual improvement in FVC_p in nintedanib treatment vs. patients treated with a placebo (Flaherty et al. 2018). INPULSIS I and II trials revealed that nintedanib significantly slowed disease progression, reducing the decline rate of FVC_p (Fala 2015). Moreover, the TOMORROW trial showed a 68% reduction in the annual decline rate of FVC_p for the nintedanib group compared with the placebo group (Richeldi et al. 2018).

Regarding HRCT, after six months, the current study findings showed radiological changes as increasing, decreasing, or remaining the same in GGO and consolidation, honeycombing, and reticulation. There was a decrease in GGO and consolidation in 46.15% for the pirfenidone group vs. 50% for nintedanib. Stationary HRCT findings (the same as baseline) regarding GGO and consolidation were found in 30.76% and 20.83% for pirfenidone and nintedanib groups, respectively. The same changes as the baseline regarding honeycombing and reticulation were found in 76.92% and 87.5% of the pirfenidone and nintedanib groups, respectively. Increases in GGO and consolidation were found in 23.07% and 29.16% for the pirfenidone and nintedanib groups, respectively. Radiological increases in the area of honeycombing and reticulation were found in 23.07% for the pirfenidone group vs. 12.5% for the nintedanib group without a significant difference between the two groups regarding HRCT changes in either GGO or honeycombing.

Ikeda et al. reported that the radiological pattern of fibrosis was significantly reduced in patients treated with pirfenidone compared to the control group (Ikeda et al. 2022). Moreover, Nakano et al. reported that HRCT findings revealed reduced areas of GGO and consolidation after four months of treatment with nintedanib (Nakano et al. 2019). Sadon et al. disagreed with our result and showed a significant difference between the pirfenidone vs. nintedanib groups regarding HRCT changes (Sadon et al. 2020).

Molecular biomarkers are urgently needed to improve the prognosis of chronic lung disease. Therefore, identifying easily detectable specific serum biomarkers is of great value (Sadon et al. 2020). When alveolar epithelial cells are damaged, KL-6 is released from these cells and can be detected in blood (Sadon et al. 2020).

In the current study, serum KL-6 was significantly elevated in untreated patients compared to those receiving either pirfenidone or nintedanib. Additionally, there is an inverse correlation with FVC_p and $SPO_2\%$ and a direct significant correlation with mMRC, indicating that this marker has predictive ability to predict treatment response with a lower value correlated with better response. Similar results were observed with the CCL-18 biomarker.

In their study, Yang et al. showed that TGF- β 1 promotes JAK2 phosphorylation, and blocking the TGF- β 1/TGF- β R signaling pathway inhibits JAK2 phosphorylation,

decreasing KL-6 levels (Yang et al. 2024). This may represent one of the antifibrotic mechanisms of pirfenidone and nintedanib. Nakano et al. showed that treatment with nintedanib decreased the serum level of KL-6 (Nakano et al. 2019). Another study reported that some tyrosine kinase inhibitors, such as nintedanib, can strongly inhibit the TGF- β 1/Smad3 signaling pathway, suggesting that tyrosine kinase inhibitors also have a relationship with the TGF- β 1 signaling pathway (Miao et al. 2023).

The mechanism by which nintedanib can decrease the level of CCL-18 can be explained through a study done by Tendon et al.. This experimental study on the bleomycin model of fibrosis demonstrates that macrophages treated with nintedanib attenuated the transition of fibroblasts to myofibroblasts compared to hyperpolarized macrophages. This myofibroblast transition is thought to occur through CCL18 and TGF-B secretion. CCL18 acted synergistically with TGF-B to cause the transition of fibroblasts to myofibroblasts (Tandon et al. 2017). Another mechanism nintedanib prevents IL-6-mediated CCL-18 secretion and subsequent myofibroblast transition in vitro. These results suggest that the antifibrotic effect of nintedanib observed in IPF patients may be associated with its effect on reducing CCL-18 secretion by alternatively activated macrophages (Ask et al. 2017).

Majewski et al. found that the serum level of CCL-18 insignificantly decreased during treatment with nintedanib (Majewski et al. 2021). Pirfenidone decreased the level of CCL-18 by inhibiting the production and activity of transforming growth factor-beta (TGF- β), a key cytokine involved in the fibrotic response. TGF- β stimulates the Smad pathway, which promotes the transcription of profibrotic genes, including those involved in producing extracellular matrix proteins and chemokines like CCL18 (Antar et al. 2022). Furthermore, pirfenidone has been shown to inhibit the Signal Transducer and Activator of the Transcription 6 (STAT6) pathway. STAT6 was activated by cytokines like IL-4 and IL-13, which were involved in the alternative activation of M2 macrophages. M2 macrophages produced high levels of CCL18 (Saito et al. 2016). Bonella et al. showed a negative correlation between CCL-18 and a decline in FVC_p after 12 months of treatment with pirfenidone (Bonella et al. 2014).

No other study examined the effect of nintedanib on the level of CCL-18 in vivo; other studies demonstrated the mechanism of action of nintedanib and its effect on the level of CCL-18 in vitro. Furthermore, there were no additional studies that compared nintedanib and pirfenidone regarding CCL-18 biomarkers.

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Most of our patients showed gastrointestinal adverse drug reaction (ADR), with diarrhea being the most common side effect, especially with pirfenidone. These patients were treated symptomatically. Hepatic enzyme elevation was observed mostly with nintedanib, which either spontaneously reduced over time or reduced the dose to 100 mg twice daily, resolving the elevation in hepatic enzymes. In addition to diarrhea, skin rash, pigmentation, and stomach pain were the most common side effects of pirfenidone. The CAPACITY trials (Noble et al. 2011), ASCEND trials (King et al. 2014), and INPULSIS-1 and INPULSIS-2 trials (Richeldi et al. 2014) reported similar results.

After the introduction of nintedanib and pirfenidone as new treatment modalities for IPF, we recommend using one of the newer antifibrotic drugs. These drugs offer new hope in treating patients with IPF because they offer improved clinical, functional, or radiological outcomes over conventional treatment.

Study limitation

First, as this study was retrospective, a selection bias might exist concerning the introduction of antifibrotic medication for patients with IPF. Our study's follow-up time was short, about six months. The study examined a single ethnic group, the Iraqi Arabic population, which limits its generalizability.

Conclusions

Nintedanib and pirfenidone have been used to effectively treat IPF worldwide. Both drugs have demonstrated the capacity to postpone the beginning stages of FVC_p decrease and lung function decline. There was little difference between the efficacy of nintedanib and pirfenidone. Both drugs were safe and well tolerated for the treatment of IPF. However, there is currently no treatment available for the already damaged lung, which worsens with time. Future research should focus on early detection of the disease and timely initiation of drug administration, reversal of fibrosis in the lungs, and lowering patient mortality from IPF.

Data availability

Zenodo: Al-Sarraf, W. A. Jabbar (2024) IPF treatment in Iraq [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12531920>.

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